

Appendix

**“Do Citizens Judge Health Experts Through a Partisan Lens?
Evidence from a Factorial Survey Experiment” by Anina Hanimann
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Response Rate

The article uses a sample of citizens from the German- and French-speaking region of Switzerland, which is drawn from a high-quality sample frame. The latter relies on data from population registers, which are updated every three months (Federal Statistical Office FSO 2020). The Federal Statistical Office (FSO) provided 8,287 mailing addresses, 8,135 of which were valid. Respondents received an invitation to the survey and two reminder letters by mail between May 1 and July 8, 2019. The table below reports the response rate.

Table A1. Calculation of Citizens' Response Rate

	Code	N
<i>Interview</i>	Complete	2,465
	Partial	76
<i>Eligible, non-interview</i>	Refusal	163
<i>Unknown eligibility, non-interview</i>	No response	5,322
	No valid mail address available	152
<i>I=Complete interviews</i>	1.1	2,465
<i>P=Partial interviews</i>	1.2	76
<i>R=Refusal and break off</i>	2.1	163
<i>NC=Non-contact</i>	2.2	0
<i>O=Other</i>	2.0/2.3	109
Response Rate 1		29.7%
Response Rate 2		30.7%

Note: Response rates are calculated based on the AAPOR Response Rate Calculator V4.0. I assumed a proportion of 100% for unknown eligibility because I relied on address lists provided by the Federal Statistical Office.

Experimental Treatments

Table A2. Number of Observations in the Experimental Conditions

Condition	Statement manipulation	n
3	Academic x Opinion-based x High Advocacy x FV	202
4	Academic x Opinion-based x High Advocacy x CCS	205
5	Academic x Evidence-based x Low Advocacy x FV	207
6	Academic x Evidence-based x Low Advocacy x CCS	204
9	Administration x Opinion-based x Low Advocacy x FV	206
12	Administration x Opinion-based x High Advocacy x CCS	206
14	Administration x Evidence-based x Low Advocacy x CCS	201
15	Administration x Evidence-based x High Advocacy x FV	209
17	Corporation x Opinion-based x Low Advocacy x FV	208
18	Corporation x Opinion-based x Low Advocacy x CCS	201
23	Corporation x Evidence-based x High Advocacy x FV	210
24	Corporation x Evidence-based x High Advocacy x CCS	206

Note: FV=flu vaccination, CCS=colorectal cancer screening

Figure A1. Presentation of the Expert Quote

Note: The image is a screenshot from the online survey, which was conducted using the Qualtrics software.

Table A3. Wording of the Experimental Treatments (translated from the German/French)

Variables	Values	Flu vaccination	Colorectal cancer screening
Type of expert	Academic	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get a flu vaccination. The following quote from <i>an expert from a Swiss university</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of vaccinations: ..., said the expert from the <i>university</i> .	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get colorectal cancer screening tests. The following quote from <i>an expert from a Swiss university</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of cancer prevention: ..., said the expert from the <i>university</i> .
	Administration	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get a flu vaccination. The following quote from <i>an expert from the responsible federal agency</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of vaccinations: ..., said the expert from the <i>federal agency</i> .	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get colorectal cancer screening tests. The following quote from <i>an expert from the responsible federal agency</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of cancer prevention: ..., said the expert from the <i>federal agency</i> .
	Corporation	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get a flu vaccination. The following quote from <i>an expert from a Swiss pharmaceutical company</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of vaccinations: ..., said the expert from the <i>pharmaceutical company</i> .	There are repeated calls for politicians to take measures to encourage more people to get colorectal cancer screening tests. The following quote from <i>an expert from a Swiss pharmaceutical company</i> appeared in a newspaper article. The quoted expert is a leader in the field of cancer prevention: ..., said the expert from the <i>pharmaceutical company</i> .
Evidence base	Evidence-based	<i>According to current figures</i> , several hundred people die from influenza every year.	<i>According to current figures</i> , almost two thousand people die from colorectal cancer every year. The right measures could prevent or at least reduce these deaths.

Variables	Values	Flu vaccination	Colorectal cancer screening
		<p>The right measures could prevent or at least reduce these deaths.¹</p> <p><i>Studies show</i> that flu vaccination can effectively reduce the number of flu cases.</p> <p><i>The data also confirm</i> that serious side effects due to influenza vaccination are very rare.</p>	<p><i>Studies show</i> that colorectal cancer screening tests can effectively reduce the number of colorectal cancer cases.</p> <p><i>The data also confirm</i> that serious side effects due to colorectal cancer screening tests are very rare.</p>
	Opinion-based	<p><i>I estimate</i> that several hundred people die from the flu every year.</p> <p>The right measures could prevent or at least reduce these deaths.</p> <p><i>I am convinced</i> that flu vaccination can effectively reduce the number of flu cases.</p> <p><i>As far as I know</i>, serious side effects of the flu vaccination are very rare.</p>	<p><i>I estimate</i> that almost two thousand people die from colorectal cancer every year.</p> <p>The right measures could prevent or at least reduce these deaths.</p> <p><i>I am convinced</i> that colorectal cancer screening tests can effectively reduce the number of colorectal cancer cases.</p> <p><i>As far as I know</i>, serious side effects due to colorectal cancer screening tests are very rare.</p>
Degree of advocacy	High	It is therefore imperative that politicians invest more money in information campaigns, because this means that more people from risk groups and from the latter's environment will take advantage of vaccination.	It is therefore imperative that politicians invest more money in information campaigns, because this means that more people from risk groups will take advantage of colorectal cancer screening tests.
	Low	In the future, politicians could therefore examine which measures could help ensure that more people from risk groups and from the latter's environment will take advantage of vaccination	In the future, politicians could therefore examine which measures could help ensure that more people from risk groups will take advantage of colorectal cancer screening tests.

Note: The table contains a translation of the original treatments used to create the quotes. The experiment was conducted in French and German.

¹ This sentence was identical for both issues.

Sample

Table A4. Sample Description

	Sample		Population
	N	%	%
Age (M=49,7; SD=17.3)			
18-39	770	31.3	31.2
40-64	1,173	47.7	42.1
< 64	518	21.0	26.7
N	2,461	100.0	100.0
Sex			
Female	1,230	50.1	50.4
Male	1,226	49.9	49.6
N	2,456	100.0	100.0
Language region			
German-speaking	1,626	66.0	76.8
French-speaking	836	34.0	23.2
N	2,462	100.0	100.0
Partisanship			
Left-wing	687	28.0 (35.6)	31.9
Center	856	34.9 (44.3)	39.2
Right-wing	389	15.9 (20.1)	27.5
No ties	520	21.2	-
N	2,452	100.0	98.6

Source: Bundesamt für Statistik (BFS) [Federal Statistical Office (FSO)] (2018, 2019a, 2019b).

The FSO provided the author with data on the shares of citizens in each region upon request.

Note: The population consists of all Swiss citizens aged 18 and higher in the German- and French-speaking regions of Switzerland. Population shares by age and gender were only available for the whole of Switzerland (i.e., including the Italian-speaking part). The population's shares by partisanship do not add up to 100% because some parties could not be classified as either right, center or left based on the data from the FSO. The percentages in brackets indicate the share excluding citizens with no ties to allow for comparison with the whole population.

Randomization

Table A5. Randomization Checks Across the Experimental Groups

Vignette		Groups												
		All	3	4	5	6	9	12	14	15	17	18	23	24
<i>Sex (male)</i>		49.9	51.0	49.8	52.7	49.0	43.7	53.2	48.7	52.2	46.9	54.0	49.0	49.0
<i>Age</i>														
	18-39	31.3	33.2	33.2	35.4	33.3	32.5	31.2	23.1	27.3	33.2	33.3	26.7	33.0
	40-64	47.7	48.5	49.8	44.2	48.0	45.2	48.3	52.3	49.3	46.6	42.3	50.5	47.1
	> 64	21.0	18.3	17.1	20.4	18.6	22.3	20.5	24.6	23.5	20.2	24.4	22.9	19.9
<i>Tertiary education</i>		25.5	24.5	27.0	23.9	29.8	29.1	26.6	22.4	28.1	23.8	22.7	25.1	22.8
<i>Partisanship</i>														
	Left	28.0	25.4	26.3	28.3	29.1	27.2	35.4	29.9	27.5	26.8	24.1	34.5	21.5
	Centre	34.9	37.3	39.5	32.2	30.5	35.9	29.6	31.3	34.8	36.1	37.7	35.4	38.5
	Right	15.9	18.9	13.7	16.6	21.2	12.6	12.1	19.4	17.9	13.7	17.6	13.9	13.2
	No ties	21.2	18.4	20.5	22.9	19.2	24.3	22.8	19.4	19.8	23.4	20.6	16.3	26.8
<i>N</i>		2,465	202	205	207	204	206	206	201	209	208	201	210	206

Note: The table shows that, for example, male respondents, respondents aged 40 to 64 years, and citizens supporting center parties were overrepresented in some groups. However, Pearson's Chi-squared tests indicate that this has not lead to significant imbalances on specific values of the treatment variables (e.g., that males evaluated quotes from academic experts significantly more often than females).

Question Wording and Summary Statistics of the Dependent and the Independent Variables

Table A6. Information About the Variables Used in the Analysis

Variable name	Description	Original wording in survey (translated from German/French)
expert credibility (mean additive index)	N=2,405 M=4.79 SD=1.31 Min: 1 Max: 7 $\alpha_{std}=0.95$ IIC=0.75	What qualities would you ascribe to the expert quoted? Please make a decision for each adjective pair: [competent/incompetent, well trained/ill-trained, experienced/inexperienced, sincere/insincere, fair/unfair, trustworthy/untrustworthy; scale from 1 to 7]
intention to take personal action (continuous variable)	N=2,288 M=3.38 SD=2.26 Min: 1 Max: 7	Based on the expert citation you have read, how likely is it that you will [get a flu shot/get a colorectal cancer screening test]? [very unlikely, 1, 2...7, very likely, don't know]
Partisanship (categorical variable)	N=2,452 <i>Shares:</i> right-wing=15.86% center=34.91% left-wing=28.02% no ties=21.21%	If the National Council were elected today, which party would you vote for? [SVP/UDC (Swiss People's Party), SPS/PSS (Social Democratic Party), FDP/PRD (Liberal Party), CVP/PDC (Christian Democratic Party), GPS/PES (Green Party), BDP/PBD (Conservative Democratic Party), glp/vert'libéraux (Green Liberal Party), other party (please indicate), I would not vote, I don't know] Subsequently, the answer categories were categorized into right, center or left based on the rile-index from the Party Manifesto Project data 2019 (Volkens et al. 2020): Right: SVP/UDC, other right-wing parties (open text field) [index values > 20] Center: FDP/PRD, CVP/PDC, BDP/PBD, GLP/vert'libéraux, other center parties (open text field) [-20 ≤ index values ≤ 20]

Variable name	Description	Original wording in survey (translated from German/French)
		<p>Left: GPS/PES, SPS/PSS, other left-wing parties (open text field) [index values < -20]</p> <p>As citizens without party ties, I categorized all citizens who indicated in the open text box to not have ties to a party, who indicated not having an intention to vote or not to know which party to vote for.</p>
prior attitudes (mean additive index)	<p><i>Flu:</i> N=1,238 M=3.85 SD=1.19 Min: 1 Max: 7 α_{std}=0.72 IIC=0.34</p> <p><i>CCS:</i> N=1,222 M=4.46 SD=1.05 Min: 1 Max: 7 α_{std}=0.62 IIC=0.25</p>	<p>To what extent do you agree with the following statements?</p> <p><i>Flu vaccination:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The risks of influenza are exaggerated. [reverse coded item] - Flu vaccination is risky. [reverse coded item] - Flu vaccination can effectively prevent influenza. - Instead of getting a flu shot, people had better go through the flu naturally. [reverse coded item] - The pharmaceutical companies in particular are doing business with the scaremongering surrounding flu epidemics. [reverse coded item] <p><i>Colorectal cancer screening:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The risks of colon cancer are exaggerated. [reverse coded item] - Colorectal cancer screening is risky. [reverse coded item] - Colorectal cancer screening can effectively prevent colon cancer. - Instead of getting screened for colon cancer, people had better maintain a healthy lifestyle. [reverse coded item] - The pharmaceutical companies in particular are making a business out of scaremongering surrounding colon cancer. [reverse coded item] <p>[completely disagree, 1,2,...7 completely agree, don't know]</p>
occupation in health (dummy variable)	<p>N=2,434</p> <p><i>Shares:</i> no=79.54% yes=20.46%</p>	<p>Are you professionally active in the healthcare sector, have you ever worked in this field or do you have any training in the healthcare sector? [yes, no]</p>

Variable name	Description	Original wording in survey (translated from German/French)
gender (dummy variable)	N=2,456 <i>Shares:</i> male=49.92% female=50.08%	Please indicate your sex: [male, female, other]
education (dummy variable)	N=2,384 <i>Shares:</i> tertiary=25.50% other=74.50%	What is the highest education or the highest training certificate you have received? [no completed school education, compulsory school, apprenticeship/vocational school, high school/primary teacher training, higher technical and vocational training, higher technical college, university/university of applied sciences, don't know] Recoded into "tertiary education" (i.e., university/university of applied sciences) and "other"
age (continuous variable)	N=2,461 M=49.73 SD=17.28 Min: 19 Max: 111	What year were you born? [younger than 18, ..., 1908] Note: Even though the sample frame should guarantee that no respondents younger than 18 are contacted, the category "younger than 18" was included. Respondents who chose this category were screened out.
Region (dummy variable)	N=2,462 <i>Shares:</i> German=66.00% French=34.00%	Coded based on information contained in the sample frame.

Note: flu=flu vaccination, ccs=colorectal cancer screening

Distribution of Issue Attitudes

Figure A2. Distribution of Prior Attitudes Toward Flu Vaccination

Note: The figure displays the frequency distribution of the index of prior attitudes towards flu vaccination. 1 stands for “weak support for flu vaccination,” while 7 denotes “strong support for flu vaccination.”

Figure A3. Prior Attitudes Toward Flu Vaccination by Partisanship

Note: The figure displays citizens' mean support (mean index) for flu vaccination by partisanship. 1 stands for "weak support for flu vaccination" and 7 for "strong support for flu vaccination." The differences between centrist and right-wing citizens ($M_{center}=3.99$, $M_{right}=3.62$, $p=0.004$), between centrist citizens and citizens without party ties ($M_{noties}=3.74$, $p=0.066$), and between right-wing and left-wing citizens are significant ($M_{left}=3.87$, $p=0.045$).

Figure A4. Distribution of Prior Attitudes Toward Colorectal Cancer Screening

Note: The figure displays the frequency distribution of the index of prior attitudes towards colorectal cancer screening. 1 stands for “weak support for colorectal cancer screening,” while 7 denotes “strong support for colorectal cancer screening.”

Figure A5. Prior Attitudes Toward Colorectal Cancer Screening by Partisanship

Note: The figure displays mean support (mean index) for colorectal cancer screening by partisanship. 1 stands for “weak support for colorectal cancer screening,” while 7 denotes “strong support for colorectal cancer screening”. The differences between centrist and right-wing citizens ($M_{\text{center}}=4.68$, $M_{\text{right}}=4.32$, $p=0.000$), between centrist and left-wing citizens ($M_{\text{left}}=4.46$, $p=0.011$), between citizens with no party ties and left-wing citizens ($M_{\text{noties}}=4.21$, $p=0.002$), and between citizens with no party ties and centrist citizens are significant ($p=0.000$).

Pretests & Manipulation Checks

I conducted a first pretest in Fall 2018. This pretest sought to test the meaning and the effectiveness of the planned experimental treatments (e.g., Do the respondents describe the type of expert as expected?) (Hauser, Ellsworth, and Gonzalez 2018). To do so, I fielded a short survey of 310 Belgian and Swiss university students. The respondents randomly received one of the 12 sampled expert quotations. After reading the quote, they answered a series of questions for the purposes of the manipulation checks (e.g., “Can you remember who the expert whose statement you just read was?”). An open-ended question was included to receive feedbacks about the authenticity of the quotation. The results indicated that, overall, the treatments worked quite well. Nevertheless, I strengthened the treatments for expert type for the second pretest because the respondents recalling the expert. Moreover, the treatment of the evidence base was slightly weakened so as not to overpower the other effects. In a second pretest among 728 Swiss citizens at the beginning of 2019 using the Dynata panel, I tested the final survey with the actual experiment. In addition to validating the effectiveness of the treatments, this pretest also helped validate my measure for expert credibility. This second pretest confirmed that the treatments were effective. Moreover, it helped me derive a valid and reliable measure for expert credibility based on six items.

The manipulation checks in the final survey confirmed that most treatments were effective. For two of the three manipulated expert affiliations, a majority of citizens correctly remembered where the expert whose quotation they had read came from. Academic experts were correctly remembered most often (62.0%), followed by corporation experts (55.0%). However, citizens only remembered administration experts correctly in 35.3% of all cases. Citizens also correctly remembered whether the expert advocated for a specific policy or not ($M_{\text{advocacy-weak}}=3.85$, $M_{\text{advocacy-strong}}=4.26$, $p=0.000$). They perceived experts advocating for specific policies as significantly more motivated

to persuade than to inform ($M_{\text{advocacy-strong}}=3.93$, $M_{\text{advocacy-weak}}=4.20$, $p=0.003$) and as having a clear position on the issue ($M_{\text{advocacy-strong}}=5.74$, $M_{\text{advocacy-weak}}=5.58$, $p=0.015$). Finally, citizens correctly identified whether the citation was evidence-based or opinion-based ($M_{\text{evidence-base}}=3.79$, $M_{\text{opinion-based}}=4.31$, $p=0.000$). Citizens who failed the manipulation checks were kept in the sample to maintain symmetry across the different conditions (Aronow, Pinson, and Baron 2015). However, Table A8 runs the same models on a reduced sample that excludes the citizens who failed the manipulation checks.

Flu vaccination (FV) and colorectal cancer screening (CCS) uptake in Switzerland

Data of the Federal Statistical Office show, that 31 percent of the Swiss population has at last once vaccinated against flu, for colorectal cancer screening the share ranges between 28 to 34 percent (depending on the test procedure). While the uptake of both prevention measures is relatively similar, we can identify differences depending on the language region of interest for the present study: there are fewer citizens in the German speaking part of Switzerland who indicate not having had a colorectal cancer screening test (65.6%-70.6% depending on the test) than in the French speaking part (68.1%-80.7% depending on the test). For flu vaccination, uptake is higher in the French speaking part than in the German speaking part: for the French speaking part 63.6% indicating never having had a flu vaccination while the respective share for the German speaking part is at 69.2% (Bundesamt für Statistik BFS 2012).²

² Source: <http://www.portal-stat.admin.ch/sgb2012/files/de/02c8.xml>; accessed : 14th October 2022. While the data for the flu vaccination is for the whole population, the data for the colorectal cancer screening is only for people aged 40 and higher.

Detailed Model Output

Table A7. Models for Expert Credibility (Models 1, 3, and 5) and Intention to Take Personal Action (Models 2, 4, and 6)

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Intercept	4.42*** (0.08)	2.86*** (0.12)	4.23*** (0.10)	2.70*** (0.14)	4.46*** (0.09)	2.81*** (0.14)
<i>Main effects</i>						
Type of expert						
Academic/Corporation	0.33*** (0.06)	0.24** (0.09)	0.60*** (0.11)	0.44** (0.16)	0.33*** (0.06)	0.25** (0.09)
Administration/Corporation	.36*** (0.06)	0.42*** (0.09)	0.63*** (0.10)	0.71*** (0.16)	0.36*** (0.06)	0.42*** (0.09)
Advocacy	-0.09* (0.05)	-0.15* (0.08)	-0.09* (0.05)	-0.15* (0.08)	-0.16 [†] (0.09)	-0.03 (0.13)
Partisanship						
Center/Left	0.06 (0.06)	-0.05 (0.10)	0.27** (0.10)	0.18 (0.16)	-0.03 (0.08)	0.01 (0.14)
Right/Left	-0.20* (0.08)	-0.11 (0.12)	0.17 (0.12)	-0.09 (0.21)	-0.17 (0.10)	0.11 (0.17)
No ties/Left	-0.10 (0.07)	0.07 (0.12)	0.17 (0.12)	0.44* (0.19)	0.14 (0.10)	0.09 (0.15)

Table A7 continued

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
<i>Interaction with type of expert</i>						
Center x						
Academic/Corporation	-	-	-0.36* (0.14)	-0.25 (0.23)	-	-
Administration/Corporation	-	-	-0.25 [†] (0.14)	-0.44 [†] (0.23)	-	-
Right x						
Academic/Corporation	-	-	-0.51** (0.17)	0.00 (0.28)	-	-
Administration/Corporation	-	-	-0.55** (0.18)	-0.09 (0.28)	-	-
No ties x						
Academic/Corporation	-	-	-0.30 [†] (0.17)	-0.54 [†] (0.27)	-	-
Administration/Corporation	-	-	-0.51** (0.16)	-0.57* (0.27)	-	-
<i>Interaction with advocacy</i>						
Center x						
strong/weak advocacy	-	-	-	-	0.18 (0.11)	-0.12 (0.19)
Right x						
strong/weak advocacy					-0.07 (0.15)	-0.46* (0.23)
No ties x						
strong/weak advocacy	-	-	-	-	0.07 (0.14)	-0.03 (0.23)

Table A7 continued

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
<i>Controls</i>						
Evidence-based statement	0.12* (0.05)	0.22** (0.08)	0.12** (0.05)	0.22** (0.08)	0.11* (0.05)	0.21** (0.08)
Colorectal cancer screening	0.17*** (0.05)	0.47*** (0.08)	0.16*** (0.05)	0.46*** (0.08)	0.16*** (0.05)	0.46*** (0.08)
Positive prior attitude	0.46*** (0.02)	1.02*** (0.03)	0.46*** (0.02)	1.02*** (0.03)	0.46*** (0.02)	1.02*** (0.03)
Occupation/education in health sector	0.09 (0.06)	0.03 (0.10)	0.08 (0.06)	0.03 (0.10)	0.08 (0.06)	0.03 (0.10)
Tertiary education	0.01 (0.06)	-0.16 [†] (0.10)	0.01 (0.05)	-0.16 [†] (0.09)	0.01 (0.06)	-0.16 [†] (0.09)
Age	0.00* (0.00)	0.02*** (0.00)	0.00* (0.00)	0.02*** (0.00)	0.00* (0.00)	0.02*** (0.00)
Gender (female)	0.00 (0.05)	-0.09 (0.08)	0.01 (0.05)	-0.08 (0.08)	0.00 (0.05)	-0.09 (0.08)
French-speaking Switzerland	0.30*** (0.05)	0.45*** (0.09)	0.30*** (0.05)	0.46*** (0.09)	0.29*** (0.05)	0.45*** (0.09)
R ²	0.25	0.37	0.25	0.37	0.25	0.37
Adj. R ²	0.24	0.36	0.25	0.36	0.24	0.36
N	2,306	2,220	2,306	2,220	2,306	2,220
RMSE (normalized)	0.18	0.30	0.18	0.30	0.18	0.30

***p<.001, **p<.01, *p<.05, [†]p<.1.

Note: Coefficients and standard errors (in parentheses) regression models (OLS) with robust standard errors. The variables ‘prior attitude’ and ‘age’ were centered. The dependent variable of models 1, 3, and 5 is expert credibility. For models 2, 4, and 6, it is intention to take personal action.

Robustness Checks

Table A8. Robustness Check: Models Excluding Citizens Who Failed the Manipulation Check

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Intercept	4.41*** (0.17)	2.65*** (0.27)	4.33*** (0.12)	2.61*** (0.18)	4.44*** (0.12)	2.70*** (0.18)
<i>Main effects</i>						
Type of expert						
Academic/Corporation	0.55*** (0.11)	0.44* (0.20)	0.69*** (0.13)	0.69*** (0.19)	0.39*** (0.07)	0.21 [†] (0.12)
Administration/Corporation	0.36** (0.14)	0.45 [†] (0.23)	0.75*** (0.13)	0.71** (0.24)	0.43*** (0.07)	0.46*** (0.12)
Advocacy	-0.18 [†] (0.10)	-0.26 (0.17)	-0.09 (0.06)	-0.12 (0.10)	-0.20 [†] (0.11)	-0.03 (0.17)
Partisanship						
Center/Left	-0.12 (0.12)	-0.13 (0.21)	0.15 (0.12)	0.19 (0.19)	-0.11 (0.11)	0.04 (0.18)
Right/Left	-0.46** (0.17)	-0.11 (0.26)	0.14 (0.16)	-0.05 (0.26)	-0.25 [†] (0.14)	-0.17 (0.22)
No ties/Left	-0.19 (0.15)	0.12 (0.25)	0.16 (0.15)	0.20 (0.25)	-0.08 (0.14)	0.35 (0.21)

Table A8 continued

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
<i>Interaction with type of expert</i>						
Center x						
Academic/Corporation	-	-	-0.16 (0.17)	-0.36 (0.28)	-	-
Administration/Corporation	-	-	-0.38* (0.19)	-0.67* (0.34)	-	-
Right x						
Academic/Corporation	-	-	-0.54* (0.22)	-0.27 (0.36)	-	-
Administration/Corporation	-	-	-0.77** (0.25)	-0.04 (0.41)	-	-
No ties x						
Academic/Corporation			-0.18 (0.21)	-0.39 (0.35)		
Administration/Corporation			-0.58* (0.25)	-0.36 (0.41)		

Table A8 continued

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
<i>Interaction with advocacy</i>						
Center x						
strong/weak advocacy	-	-	-	-	0.23 (0.15)	-0.12 (0.24)
Right x						
strong/weak advocacy	-	-	-	-	-0.04 (0.18)	-0.07 (0.28)
No ties x						
strong/weak advocacy			-	-	-0.08 (0.18)	-0.30 (0.29)
R ²	0.32	0.35	0.31	0.40	0.26	0.36
Adj. R ²	0.30	0.32	0.30	0.39	0.25	0.36
N	463	448	1,196	1,158	1,412	1,353
RMSE (normalized)	0.17	0.30	0.17	0.29	0.18	0.30

***p<0.001, **p<0.01, *p<0.05, †p<0.1.

Note: Coefficients and standard errors (in parentheses) from linear regression models (OLS) with robust standard errors. Not reported are the control variables included in all of the models (see Table A7). The dependent variable of models 1, 3, and 5 is expert credibility. For models 2, 4, and 6, it is intention to take personal action. Models 1 and 2 include citizens who passed all manipulation checks; models 3 through 6 only include those who passed the manipulation check for ‘expert type’ and ‘advocacy’, respectively. The partisan groups are represented similarly in the full sample and in all of the subsamples.

Table A9. Robustness Check: Models With Different Missing Handling (mean imputed & additional category)

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Intercept	4.46*** (0.08)	2.93*** (0.12)	4.30*** (0.10)	2.81*** (0.14)	4.49*** (0.09)	2.87*** (0.13)
<i>Main effects</i>						
Type of expert						
Academic/Corporation	0.30*** (0.06)	0.23** (0.09)	0.52*** (0.11)	0.33* (0.16)	0.30*** (0.06)	0.23** (0.09)
Administration/Corporation	0.35*** (0.06)	0.37*** (0.09)	0.60*** (0.10)	0.64*** (0.16)	0.36*** (0.05)	0.37*** (0.09)
Advocacy	-0.10* (0.05)	-0.14 [†] (0.07)	-0.10 (0.11)	-0.14 [†] (0.07)	-0.13 (0.08)	-0.01 (0.13)
Partisanship						
Center/Left	0.05 (0.06)	-0.06 (0.09)	0.23* (0.10)	0.08 (0.15)	-0.03 (0.08)	0.00 (0.13)
Right/Left	-0.21** (0.07)	-0.12 (0.12)	0.12 (0.12)	-0.11 (0.19)	-0.17 [†] (0.10)	0.09 (0.16)
No ties/Left	-0.14* (0.07)	0.03 (0.10)	0.09 (0.11)	0.35* (0.18)	-0.12 (0.10)	0.05 (0.14)
Missing	0.00 (0.34)	-1.00* (0.44)	0.02 (0.53)	-0.50 (0.81)	-0.17 (0.52)	-0.75 (0.70)

Table A9 continued

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
<i>Interaction with type of expert</i>						
Center x						
Academic/Corporation	-	-	-0.28* (0.14)	-0.08 (0.22)	-	-
Administration/Corporation	-	-	-0.24 [†] (0.14)	-0.35 (0.22)	-	-
Right x						
Academic/Corporation	-	-	-0.44* (0.17)	0.06 (0.27)	-	-
Administration/Corporation	-	-	-0.52** (0.17)	-0.08 (0.27)	-	-
No ties x						
Academic/Corporation	-	-	-0.24 (0.17)	-0.35 (0.25)	-	-
Administration/Corporation	-	-	-0.42** (0.16)	-0.61* (0.25)	-	-
Missing x						
Academic/Corporation	-	-	0.07 (0.85)	-0.69 (0.83)	-	-
Administration/Corporation	-	-	0.07 (0.54)	-1.43 [†] (0.82)	-	-

Table A9 continued

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
<i>Interaction with advocacy</i>						
Center x						
strong/weak advocacy	-	-	-	-	0.16 (0.11)	-0.13 (0.18)
Right x						
strong/weak advocacy	-	-	-	-	-0.09 (0.14)	-0.44* (0.22)
No ties x						
strong/weak advocacy	-	-	-	-	-0.04 (0.14)	-0.05 (0.20)
Missing x						
strong/weak advocacy	-	-	-	-	0.41 (0.61)	-0.57 (0.78)
R ²	0.25	0.35	0.26	0.35	0.25	0.35
Adj. R ²	0.25	0.34	0.25	0.34	0.25	0.34
N	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465
RMSE (normalized)	0.19	0.29	0.18	0.29	0.19	0.29

***p<0.001, **p<0.01, *p<0.05, †p<0.1.

Note: Note: Coefficients and standard errors (in parentheses) from linear regression models (OLS) with robust standard errors. Not reported are the control variables included in all of the models (see Table A7). The dependent variable of models 1, 3, and 5 is expert credibility. For models 2, 4, and 6, it is intention to take personal action.

Table A10. Robustness Check: Main Effects by Issue

	Model 1 Flu	Model 2 Flu	Model 1 CCS	Model 2 CCS
Intercept	4.53*** (0.10)	2.80*** (0.15)	4.44*** (0.12)	3.36*** (0.19)
<i>Main effects</i>				
Type of expert				
Academic/Corporation	0.39*** (0.08)	0.38** (0.12)	0.26*** (0.08)	0.11 (0.14)
Administration/Corporation	0.28*** (0.08)	0.33** (0.12)	0.44*** (0.08)	0.52*** (0.14)
Advocacy	-0.17* (0.07)	-0.12 (0.11)	-0.03 (0.07)	-0.15 (0.12)
Partisanship				
Center/Left	0.06 (0.08)	-0.00 (0.13)	0.08 (0.08)	-0.08 (0.15)
Right/Left	-0.29** (0.11)	-0.19 (0.16)	-0.08 (0.11)	0.00 (0.19)
No ties/Left	-0.21* (0.10)	0.25 [†] (0.15)	0.00 (0.10)	-0.09 (0.18)
<i>Controls</i>				
Evidence-based statement	0.16* (0.07)	0.18 [†] (0.11)	0.12 [†] (0.07)	0.23 [†] (0.12)
Positive prior attitude	0.47*** (0.03)	1.02*** (0.04)	0.44*** (0.03)	1.00*** (0.05)
Occupation/education in health sector	0.15 [†] (0.08)	0.05 (0.13)	0.02 (0.08)	-0.03 (0.15)
Tertiary education	0.02 (0.08)	-0.10 (0.12)	0.00 (0.08)	-0.22 (0.14)
Age	0.00 (0.00)	0.02*** (0.00)	0.00* (0.00)	0.01*** (0.00)
Gender (female)	-0.09 (0.07)	-0.14 (0.11)	0.10 (0.07)	-0.00 (0.12)
French-speaking Switzerland	0.21** (0.07)	0.48*** (0.11)	0.40*** (0.07)	0.42*** (0.13)
R ²	0.26	0.40	0.20	0.26
Adj. R ²	0.25	0.39	0.20	0.25
N	1,166	1,142	1,140	1,078
RMSE (normalized)	0.19	0.28	0.18	0.32

***p<0.001, **p<0.01, *p<0.05, [†]p<0.1.

Note: Coefficients and standard errors (in parentheses) from linear regression models (OLS) with robust standard errors. The variables ‘prior attitude’ and ‘age’ were centered. The dependent variable for models 1-Flu and 1-CCS is expert credibility. For models 2-Flu and 2-CCS, it is intention to take personal action.

Figure A6. Effect of Expert Type on Expert Credibility by Partisanship and Issue

Note: Panel A displays the effect of expert type on perceived expert credibility for each issue depending on party affiliation. Panel B plots each expert type's mean predicted values of expert credibility by respondents' party affiliation and for each issue.

Figure A7. Effect of Expert Type on Intention by Partisanship and Issue

Note: Panel A displays the effect of the expert type on intention to take personal action for each issue depending on party affiliation. Panel B plots each expert type's mean predicted values of intention by respondents' party affiliation and for each issue.

Figure A8. Effect of Advocacy on Expert Credibility by Partisanship and Issue

Note: Panel A displays the effect of advocacy on expert credibility for each issue depending on party affiliation. Panel B plots each degree of advocacy's values of expert credibility by respondents' party affiliation and for each issue.

Figure A9. Effect of Advocacy on Intention by Partisanship and Issue

Note: Panel A displays the effect of advocacy on intention to take personal action for each issue depending on party affiliation. Panel B plots Panel B plots each degree of advocacy's values of intention by respondents' party affiliation and for each issue.

Figure A10. Effect of Expert Type on Expert Credibility by Partisanship and Prior Attitudes

Note: Panel A displays the effect of expert type on expert credibility as partisanship and prior attitudes vary. Panel B plots each expert types' mean predicted values of credibility by party affiliation and depending on prior attitudes.

Figure A11. Effect of Expert Type on Intention by Partisanship and Prior Attitudes

Note: Panel A displays the effect of expert type on intention as partisanship and prior attitudes vary. Panel B plots each expert types' mean predicted values of intention by party affiliation and depending on prior attitudes.

Figure A12. Effect of Advocacy on Expert Credibility by Partisanship and Prior Attitudes

Note: Panel A displays the effect of advocacy on expert credibility as partisanship and prior attitudes vary. Panel B plots each degree of advocacy's mean predicted values of credibility by party affiliation and depending on prior attitudes.

Figure A13. Effect of Advocacy on Intention by Partisanship and Prior Attitudes

Note: Panel A displays the effect of advocacy on intention as partisanship and prior attitudes vary. Panel B plots each degree of advocacy's mean predicted values of intention by party affiliation and depending on prior attitudes.

Figure A14. Effect of Expert Type on Expert Credibility by Party Affiliation

Note: Panel A displays the effect of expert type on perceived expert credibility by party affiliation. Panel B plots each expert type's mean predicted values of credibility by respondents' party affiliation. SVP/UDC=Swiss People's Party, SPS/PSS=Social Democratic Party, GPS/PES=Green Party, glp/vert'libéraux=Green Liberal Party, CVP/PDC=Christian Democratic Party, FDP/PRD=Liberal Party, SVP/UDC=Swiss People's Party. For the other parties/answer categories, not sufficient observations were available per treatment.

Figure A15. Effect of Expert Type on Intention by Party Affiliation

Note: Panel A displays the effect of the expert type on individuals' intention to take personal action by party affiliation. Panel B plots each expert type's mean predicted values of intention to take personal action by respondents' party affiliation. SVP/UDC=Swiss People's Party, SPS/PSS=Social Democratic Party, GPS/PES=Green Party, glp/vert'libéraux=Green Liberal Party, CVP/PDC=Christian Democratic Party, FDP/PRD=Liberal Party, SVP/UDC=Swiss People's Party. For the other parties/answer categories, not sufficient observations were available per treatment.

Figure A16. Effect of Advocacy on Expert Credibility by Party Affiliation

Note: Panel A displays the effect of advocacy on perceived expert credibility by party affiliation. Panel B plots each degree of advocacy's mean predicted values of expert credibility by respondents' party affiliation. SVP/UDC=Swiss People's Party, SPS/PSS=Social Democratic Party, GPS/PES=Green Party, glp/vert'libéraux=Green Liberal Party, CVP/PDC=Christian Democratic Party, FDP/PRD=Liberal Party, SVP/UDC=Swiss People's Party. For the other parties/answer categories, not sufficient observations were available per treatment.

Figure A17. Effect of Advocacy on Intention by Party Affiliation

Note: Panel A displays the effect of advocacy on individuals' intention to take personal action by party affiliation. Panel B plots each degree of advocacy's mean predicted values of intention by respondents' party affiliation. SVP/UDC=Swiss People's Party, SPS/PSS=Social Democratic Party, GPS/PES=Green Party, glp/vert'libéraux=Green Liberal Party, CVP/PDC=Christian Democratic Party, FDP/PRD=Liberal Party, SVP/UDC=Swiss People's Party. For the other parties/answer categories, not sufficient observations were available per treatment.

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